

The Main Character's Personality "Harga Diri" and "Sebuah Usaha Melupakan" Novel Based on the Personality of Sigmund Freud

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 22, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 23, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Approach to Psychology, Literature, Sigmund Freud's Theory, Novel, Extrinsic Aspects of Novels, Main Characters</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6378100</p>	<p><i>This research examines the personality of the main characters in two Indonesian novels based on Sigmund Freud's psychoanalyst theory that explores the psychological condition of a person from the personality structure, namely the needs of norms (superego), biological needs (Id), and conditions of balance (ego). The aim of this study is to gain understanding of the meaning of a novel and motivate Indonesian literature to work to reveal the inner condition of the character, so that individuals can understand each other. The results show that while the main character's id is embodied in feelings of fear, sense of belonging, and gratification, the Ego are embodied in the state of surrender and decisionmaking. The superego includes loyalty, striving, gratitude, not complaining, and the desire to forget.</i></p>

Introduction

A thorough understanding of the meaning of a literary work requires two key aspects: reading and scientific studies. The latter enables probing into the building blocks of the work from the inside out (intrinsic and extrinsic aspects) (source).

The study of intrinsic aspects helps connoisseur of literature understand the moral values, values of care, values of sincerity infused into the novel from the reality of everyday life (source). The writers' ideasis written in language embroidered with aesthetic elements that are reflected from their choice of words that make up the aesthetic value (source).

The study of extrinsic aspects also helps connoisseurs of literary works to understand the meaning of a literary work as a whole (source). Like two sides of a coin, these two types of assessment complete each other. With the study of these two aspects, it becomes perfect to understand the meaning of literary works as a whole. In this study, literary works being investigated are "Harga Diri" and "Sebuah Usaha Melupakan" novel.

A. Theoretical Studies

1. Psychological Approach in Literature

Psychology approach in Literature is an extrinsic approach that seeks to understand the meaning of literary works from psychological perspectives as stated by Gasong (2001:245) that "The approach of psychology in literature is one that desires to know the human psyche." This approach departs from the assumption that literary works uplift human life, both physically and inwardly. The desire to understand human either in real life or in fictional literary work makes people seek psychological approaches. Basically, psychology in literature pays attention to the psychiatric problems of fictional characters in literary works, including novels (in Minderop, 2011: 54). The goal is to understand the psychological aspects contained in a literary work.

Wellek and Warren (in Wiyatmi, 2011:28) stated that "Psychology in literature has four possible understandings. The first is the study of the psychology of the author as a type or as a person, the second is the study of the creative process, the third is the study of the types and laws of psychology applied in literary works, and the fourth is the study of the impact of literature on the reader." According to Endraswara (2013: 96), The study of psychology in literature is based on the idea that work is a psychological activity.

Based on several definitions, it is concluded that psychology in literature is a science that examines characters, especially the psychological traits that are embodied in behavior and dialogue in literary works, such as novels.

2. Relationship between Literature and Psychology

Psychology and literature are two different disciplines but share something in common: both examine humans and their interactions. Literary works as a result of author's creativity and expression, which can be understood by multiple approaches, including psychology. The authors deepen their sensitivity to reality, sharpen observational skills and provide opportunities to trace previously unexplored patterns (source). Therefore, Psychology can be used by the authors to choose the character and their psychological condition in the story in order to support the storyline.

A close relation between literary works and psychology is also reported by Endraswara (2008:97-99) Psychology and literature have an indirect and functional relationship. Indirect because both have the same object, namely human life, and functional because both examine the psychology elements of people. The difference is while the symptoms in psychology are real, they are imaginative in literature.

Psychology in literature is a science that approaches literary works from a psychological point of view. Approach to Psychology in literature focuses on psychological aspects. The object of this study is text analysis (literary work) engaging the relevance and role of psychological studies, namely focusing on the characters and characterization, especially the inner conflict. With the close relationship between psychological aspects with character elements and characterizations, literary works are relevant to be analyzed psychologically in works that give intensity to psychological aspects.

In personality psychology, literature is examined because it is not merely a text, but rather a study material involving personality of characters in literary works (Minderop, 2011: 3). Human characters and their activities are explained by psychological problems. Psychological problems experienced by the characters can only be understood with the study of psychology in literature.

Based on several definitions, it can be concluded that Psychology in literature is an approach that can be used to understand the inner conflicts of the characters in literary works.

3. Psychoanalysis of Sigmund Freud

Psychoanalytic theory is concerned with human function and mentality. The theory of psychoanalysis by Sigmund Freud, according to Minderop, 2013:11, contributed to knowledge and inspired researchers in the field of psychology in literature. With these considerations, literary works contain very rich psychological aspects, so the study of psychology in literature needs to be modified and developed more seriously.

There are two assumptions that underlie Freud's Theory of Psychoanalysis, (1) assumption of psychic determinism, and (2) assumption of unconscious motivation. The assumption of psychic determinism believes that everything an individual does, thinks, or feels has meaning and purpose, and that everything is naturally predetermined. Meanwhile, the assumption of unconscious motivation believes that most individuals' behavior (such as actions, thinking, and feeling) is determined by unconscious motives.

Further, Sigmund Freud divides personality structure into three components: *id*, *ego*, and *superego*. The result of interaction of the three components makes up individual behaviour.

a. Id or Das Es

Id in Freud's term is *das es*, referring to the most basic personality system in which innate instincts dwell. For the other two systems, id is a system that acts as a provider or distributor of energy needed by those systems for the operations or activities carried out. Id cannot tolerate a build-up of energy that can lead to an overall high level of individual tension. High tension is an unpleasant condition for the individual.

Id in achieving its goals has equipment in the form of two kinds of processes. The first process is in the form of reflex action, which is a form of behavior or action whose mechanism of action is automatic and immediate and is innate of the individual. The second process is the primary process, which is a process that involves a number of complex psychological reactions. In this process, id tries to reduce the stress by forming a shadow of the object that can reduce the stress. For id, the object presented in the primary process is real, but in reality the object will not really reduce the tension. Individuals still need other systems that can lead to real stress reduction. This system is nothing but ego, however id is not affected by ego control.

Id is a personality structure carried from birth, Alwisol 2012: 13. Id contains all aspects of inherited psychology, such as instincts, impulses and drives. Id exists and operates in an unconscious area, representing subjectivity that has never been realized throughout the ages. Id is closely related to the physical process of obtaining psychic energy that is used to operate the system of other personality constructs.

Id operates on the pleasure principle, which is seeking pleasure and avoiding pain. For id, pleasure is a condition that relatively inactive state or low energy level, and pain is a tension or increased energy that craves satisfaction. The principle of pleasure is processed in two ways, by reflex action and primary processes. Reflexes are inborn automatic reactions since blinking — used to deal with the gratification of simple stimuli and are usually immediate. Examples of reflex actions are blinking, breathing, sneezing, scratching when it's itchy, laughing, smiling. The primary process is the reaction of imagining something that can reduce or eliminate the stress to deal with the stimulus that occurs. Examples of primary processes are dreams, daydreams,

and psychotic hallucinations. Id can only imagine something, but cannot distinguish fantasy from a reality that can satisfy needs. Id cannot judge or distinguish right from wrong, nor things relating to morals.

The characteristics of the personality structure of Id are psychological aspects related to human biology. Id is the source of energy for the emergence of the ego, and the super ego. Id is a pleasure principle that must be implemented immediately in order to reduce tension.

b. Ego or *Das Ich*

Ego in Freud's terms: *Das Ich* is a system that acts as an individual director to the world of objects from reality, carrying out its functions based on the principle of reality, (*the reality principle*). *Ego* is formed from the differentiation of *id* because of its contact with the outside world. The process of the *ego* relates to the efforts of satisfying the need or reducing tension is a secondary process. With this secondary process the *ego* formulates a plan to satisfy needs and tests whether the plan can be implemented or not.

Ego plays its role by involving high psychological functions, cognitive and intellectual functions. The task of *ego* is to maintain personality and ensure adjustment to the outside world. *Ego* in carrying out its function to inhibit the satisfaction of needs or instincts that come from the *id*. Acts as an intermediary of the individual's instinctive guidance, with environmental conditions. *Ego* inhibits the expression of instincts that are inappropriate or unacceptable to the environment.

Ego develops from the *id* to make a person able to deal with reality; so that the *ego* operates according to the principle of reality; Efforts to obtain satisfaction demanded by the *id* by preventing the occurrence of new tensions or delaying pleasure until an object that can actually satisfy the need is found. The principle of reality is carried out through a secondary process, namely thinking realistically, compiling a plan and testing whether the plan produces the intended object. The testing process is called reality; carry out actions according to a plan that has been thought out realistically.

Ego is the executor of personality, which has two main tasks. *First*, choosing which stimuli to respond to and/or which instincts to satisfy according to priority needs. *Second*, determine when and how the need is satisfied in accordance with the availability of opportunities with minimal risk. In other words, *ego* as a personality executive tries to fulfill the needs of the *id* while also fulfill the moral needs (*Superego*) to achieve the perfection of the *superego*. *Ego* actually works to satisfy the *id*, therefore *ego* has no energy of its own and will derive energy from the *id*.

The personality structure traits of the *ego* are psychological aspects of the personality that relate to the real world. *Ego* works for the principle of reality to reduce the tension created by the *id*. The process that the *ego* goes through is a secondary process, namely thinking realistically, such as doing reasoning, problem solving and decision making in a problem that arises.

c. Superego or *Das Ueber Ich*

Freud stated that the *super-ego* activity in the individual, especially when this activity contradicts the *ego*, expresses itself in certain emotions such as feelings of guilt and regret (Koswara, 1991: 11). Certain attitudes of individuals such as self-observation, correction or self-criticism also originate from this *super ego*.

Freud's concept, instinct or instinct is an innate psychological representation of excitation (a state of tension and arousal) in the body resulting from the emergence of a body need (Koswara, 1991: 36). Instinct will accumulate a certain amount of psychic energy when a need arises and this instinct will suppress or encourage individuals to act towards satisfying the needs that can reduce the tension caused by the pressure of the psychic energy.

Freud distinguished two kinds of instincts: death instincts and life instincts. The death instinct is an instinct aimed at destroying what already exists. The life instinct is an instinct aimed at the preservation of the *ego* (the conservation of the individual) and the maintenance of the continuity of the species (the conservation of the species).

Freud also took a great interest in the sexual instinct. Sex is meant by Freud has a broader scope than the general understanding. Psychic energy contained in the sexual instinct is called "libido" or libinal energy (Koswara, 1991: 39).

Superego is the moral and ethical force of personality, which operates using the idealistic principle as opposed to the satisfaction principle of the *id* and the realistic principle of the *ego*. The *superego* develops from the *ego*, and like the *ego* it has no energy of its own. The *superego* operates in three areas of consciousness.

Superego is essentially an element that represents parental values regarding social standards which are taught to children through various prohibitions and commands. Any behavior that is prohibited, considered wrong, and punishment by the parents will be accepted by the child as conscience, which contains anything that is not allowed. Whatever is approved, rewarded and praised by parents will be accepted as a standard of perfection or *ego* ideal, which contains everything that should be done.

The *superego* is irrational in demanding perfection, severely punishing the *ego*'s mistakes, both committed and new to the mind. The *superego* is also like the *ego* to control the *id*, not only delaying

satisfaction but hindering its fulfillment. There are three functions of the *superego*, 1) encouraging the ego to replace realistic goals with moralistic goals, 2) inhibiting the impulses of the id, especially sexual and aggressive impulses that are contrary to societal value standards, and 3) teaching perfection. The personality structure id-ego-superego is not the parts that run the personality, but is the name of a system of psychological structures and processes that follow certain principles. The traits of a superego personality structure are sociological aspects that relate much to the environment and humans themselves. *Superego* is more about the values that exist in society, such as morals, educational values, religious values. The superego transforms the principle of reality into the principle of morality in human life.

The description of the three components above is a personality system that works as a team and is governed by the ego (Yusuf, 2013: 46).

Freud divided consciousness into three:

- a. Consciousness is a part of the mental life or layers of the individual soul. The mental life of an individual has full awareness. Through this, the individual knows about who they are, what they are doing, where they are, what is happening around them, and how they get what they want.
- b. The conscious threshold is the layer of soul below consciousness, as a shelter for memories that cannot be revealed precisely, but with a certain effort something can be recalled.
- c. The unconscious is the largest layer of an individual's mental life

4. Novel

The word novel is derived from the Latin word 'Novellus' that is originated from the word 'Novus' which means 'New' in English. It is 'new' because novel is a form of literary work that came after poetry and drama. Novel as a form of literary work first appeared in English literature in the 18th century. In the Encyclopedia Americana (in Priyatni, 2010:124), "Novel is a story in prose that is rather long and reviews everyday life".

Tarigan (1991: 164-165) states, "Novel is a form of literary work which is also called fiction, novel means a work of prose fiction that is quite long. Not too long and not too short. Novels depends on the character, presenting more than one impression, more than one effect, more than one emotion.

Nurgiyantoro (2010:10) states, "Novel is a work of fiction that is built by building elements, namely intrinsic elements and extrinsic elements and is also interpreted as a prose-shaped essay that contains a series of stories of one's life with other people around him by highlighting the character and behavioral traits".

Therefore, novel is a form of literary work in the form of prose. It tells an extraordinary event from the lives of people (story characters), from the incident a conflict appeared, a dispute which changes the direction of their fate.

Novel is a literary work that serves as a place to pour the author's thoughts as a reaction to the surrounding circumstances. Novels cannot be separated from the turmoil or conditions of society involving the author and the reader. Sudjiman (Purba, 2010:63), "Novel is a long fictitious prose that presents characters and displays a series of events and settings in an organized manner". Faruk (199:29), "Novel is a story about a good search for authentic values carried out by a problematic person in a world that also heard that literature can also be learned from scientific disciplines".

Thus, it can be concluded that the novel is a long prose essay, containing a series of stories from a person's life with the people around them that highlight the character or nature of each actor.

a. Extrinsic Aspects of novels

Novel as a work of fiction is built by two elements: intrinsic and extrinsic. The intrinsic elements of a novel are the elements that directly participate in building the story. This is supported by the opinion of Nurgiyantoro (2010: 23), that "intrinsic elements are the elements that build the literary work itself". These elements cause literary works to appear as literary works, elements that factually will be found if people read literary works.

In addition to the study of intrinsic elements, namely the elements of building a novel, novels can also be studied using extrinsic approaches beyond the literary work, namely Historical, Sociological, and Psychological approaches. Therefore, extrinsic elements are all external factors that underlie literary works embedded in each approaches, such as sociological values, historical values, moral values, and psychological values (Gasong 2012:86). In turn, the actual extrinsic element is outside the literary work, help literary examiners in understanding and enjoying the literary work.

b. The Main Character in the Novel

Characters are the behaviors that exist in a fiction. Characters in literary works are essential elements, among others, that build literary work. Through characters, readers can capture the message and multiple conflicts derived from different characters built by the author.

According to Abrams (in Burhan, 2010: 165), " Exposing characters are people who are shown in a narrative or drama work which the reader interprets it as having certain morals and tendencies as expressed in speech and what is done in action". Characters of the story is author's creation; however, the characters of the story must

live naturally. According to Gasong (2012: 19), "Characters are actors who exist in a fiction". The main character, according to Wahyuningtyas and Wijaya (2011: 03) are character whose storytelling is prioritized in the prose concerned.

C. Research Methodology

This research applies descriptive qualitative method for a library research of reading materials that are relevant to this research. This literature research is supported by references in the form of novels as objects of research, as well as other supporting book sources that are related to the problems discussed in this research.

The data in this research is written data in the form of novel texts related to elements of personality of the characters using Sigmund Freud's theory.

Data sources from the novel '*Harga Diri*' and '*Sebuah Usaha Melupakanmu*'.

Techniques of collecting data are reading and note-taking techniques; data obtained from the result of reading novel text and recording information that is in accordance with the problems in this research. The data of this research were analyzed based on Sigmund Freud's Psychoanalytic approach.

D. Results and Discussion

In the following, the data and discussion are presented. In this section, due to space limitations, only part of the data is presented. The aspect studied is the behavior of the main character using Sigmund Freud's Psychoanalytic approach which includes: (1) Id, (2) Ego, (3) Superego.

Aspects of the main character's personality in the novel of *Harga Diri* by Saut Poltak Tambunan and the novel *Sebuah Usaha Melupakan* by Boy Chandra with the Psychoanalytic theory of Sigmund Freud.

Table 1
Id Data and its interpretation of "Harga Diri" Novel

Personality Structure	Data	Interpretation
Id	<i>"Do you want it, Keke?" asked Aris once again. "Yes," Anna replied after a moment of silence looking into Aris's eyes. "Because I believe in you. I also believe that your family is a good family. Like my family. And they want us to be good people." (HD, 2008:17).</i>	Anna followed her instinct without control by super ego because Anna 'agreed' to Aris' wishes. Id is a need from within humans according to Sigmund Freud's theory.
	<i>And Anna's soul was also shaken. Keke's call blew up her memory, so she realized that the moment she had been fearing had arrived. Aris has come! Aris had come to see her after a long separation! (HD, 2008:02)</i>	Anna was shaken and scared, Aris came to see her. This fear arises naturally. This becomes id's need that should immediately be avoided .
	<i>"Could it be my son is bearing the sin that I committed," thought Anna confused. "At that time, I promised Aris to say: By the devil! Yes, for the sake of the beach demon. Ah, could it be that the waiting demon really bothered my son!". (HD, 2008:31)</i>	Anna's maternal instincts emerged as manifestations of her actions. Between love for her child or admitting a mistake .
	<i>At the end of the day, Anna had to do something. She decided to meet Aris. She had to talk from heart to heart. Anna had faith, no matter how arrogant Aris is now, the man would never be able to forget Anna. The sweet memories that were once made together will not just disappear. Although now the memories have become a boomerang. "I'll be able to melt his arrogance," thought Anna, "and he should help Frans' career." (HD, 2008 48)</i>	Instinct melts arrogance and supports her husband, Frans', career. This instinct arises from within Anna with her own consideration without taking into account of external conditions or balance with the environment.
	<i>"Anna's feminine instincts spoke loudly to defend Aris's future wife. Anna wanted to prevent the marriage with all the power she has. (HD, 2008:140)</i>	Anna's desire to prevent Aris from marrying another woman. Whatever is done to achieve that goal. This is a condition of satisfying Anna's desire .

Table 2
Id Data and Its Interpretation of "Sebuah Usaha Melupakan" Novel

Personality	Data	Interpretation
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Structure		
Id	"I always imagined a future when I write a book that there will be someone who provides food for me..." (p.13)	Hallucinations of "I" character is a manifestation of the fulfilment of Id's need.
	"... He has nothing greater than his desire to be with you until then. That's why you have to be aware..." (p. 62)	The desire is with you until later, this is the longing of "I" character, which is the manifestation of the Id.
	"With you I want to age and find the end of age. With you, I want to spend everything that's left. Fight for whatever we want to have." (p. 85).	Togetherness becomes longing of "I" character. This is the Id of the "I".
	"... He only had ambitions that would slowly finish off. For him to know, you are my heart..." (p. 227)	The ambition of a 'he' who wants 'you' to be the embodiment is the form of Id of 'me'.
	"I will try to forget you. Even though every time I say that sentence there is a joy that disappears from my chest..." (Pg 238)	Unexpected loss , although it must be experienced. It's a sign that there is a need that cannot be met.
	"I want to be the one who is always by your side when the bitter sweetness hits life that embraces you. I am willing to be the body and steadfast you need; as an arm that hugs you when you feel fragile." (P. 303).	Ready to be a place to lean. It was a call from within the body of the Id of 'me'

Table 3
Ego Data and its interpretation of "Harga Diri" Novel

Personality structure	Data	Interpretation
Ego (Self-Esteem)	"No! She thought. "I will not get back because of it. Millions of children live without fathers in this world. Many people don't even have a mother at the same time. But God is merciful, God still allows them to live, go to school and work. (HD, 2008:106-107)	The determination to keep fighting is a sign of meeting the needs of Anna.
	"Dad can force me. Even any of you who are here may have the right to kick me out of this village. However, the one who suffers the torment is me." Yes, I am alone with my two children," Anna replied fiercely. Her eyes lit up. His face stiffened, against one by one the people around her. " You never explained your reasons, Anna," continued Frans' father. "I as Frans' parents do not side with any of you. But I want to know because of the divorce you want." (HD, 2008:109)	Firm on the principle of getting divorced without involving conditions outside Anna.
	"But, never mind," Anna thought as she tapped her finger on the edge of the chair. "There's no point in regretting all of it anymore. I hope Frans will forgive me. And willing to accept me back with my children." (HD, 2008:211)	The nature of surrender and hope for a better life.

Table 4
Ego Data and its interpretations of "Sebuah Usaha Melupakan" Novel

Struktur Kepribadian	Data	Interpretation
Ego	"As a person who has been writing for a few years. I once wanted to have a lover who has the same interest as me." (p. 12)	Expectation that should occur because it is not merely a necessity, but is real and does not violate

		the norm. This is the ego of 'me'.
	"... someday when I write a book. There will be someone who provides food for me. And that person is you." (Page 13).	Hopes to enjoy the pleasant conditions that are almost real.
	"distance and work require us to be patient with more patience. So that everything goes as well as possible..." (p. 75)	Be patient, from 'me' is the embodiment of the 'ego' aspect.
	"Human will always want more. The same goes for feelings. Nature of not easily satisfied and not grateful for what they have, often make a person give up what they already have." (Page 79).	Unsatisfied conditions. To always keep fighting. It is the 'ego' of 'me'.
	"... I want you to remind you in case I forget. I want to hug you if your heart hurts. With you I want to grow old and find the end of age." (p. 84-85).	Hope to please friends. It is the element of the 'ego' which has taken into account of Id's needs, and superego's consideration.
	"... I always hope that you will still be someone who is willing to be with me. No matter how hard we will have to fight. Keep being my lover. I also want to stay by your side." (P. 88).	Remain friends in joy and sorrow .
	"I have to win myself over really. Convincing myself calmly, although it is not as easy as imagined." (p. 93).	Calm is needed to overcome the problem even though it is not easy. This is embodiment of the 'ego' aspect in 'me'.
	"Publishing a poetry book is one of my big dreams. It took me almost a year to write it..." (p. 2016:140)	Make dream happens with patience .
	"I have thrown it away from my memory. Because remembering you only saturates the warmth of my day. There's no point in remembering someone who no longer wants to go home." (Pg 156).	Forgetting the past.
	"Don't be happy by hurting me. You should know, I don't even want you anymore. You, are just a part of the past that has stopped by." (Pg 163).	Forgetting the past.
	"One day you'll have to learn to realize. That I have forgotten you and are no longer important in my heart.. Every heart that is released must eventually learn to let go." (P. 251)	Learn to let go.
	"... All the things I couldn't believe finally happened. Of all that passes and we call the past. I try to make it as life lessons that will not stop because of heartbreak." (Hal 2016:246).	The spirit of rising from the past.
	"There are many jobs and dreams that I must fulfill for the sake of a promise to myself. Too much time has been wasted in the past." (Pg 266).	Commitment to self to work hard
	"All dreams and good things are also due to the warm growing passion to stay with you..." (pg. 281).	The spirit to live together
	"I want to be someone who is able to love in all circumstances. Be someone who is willing to accompany, stand upright beside me, walking hand in hand towards all the plans we are aiming for." (P. 287)	To make friends happy.
	"... I want to have a good relationship with you. Although falling cannot be separated from pain, we can still choose more carefully..." (p. 294)	Choose carefully
	"Remain someone who brings many surprises to my life with all your madness. Stay true to your big dreams. I am always willing to stand with you and grow with you." (p. 291)	To make friends happy.

	"I want to live a balanced story with you. Reciprocal feeling. Nor are the lies disguised by deceitful seduction." (p. 294).	Living together sincerely
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Table 5
Superego Data and its interpretation of "Harga Diri" Novel

Personality Structure	Data	Interpretation
Superego is the moral and ethical strength of personality, representing social standards. representative of moral values, traditional values, or values that exist in society.	"But no," argued Anna inwardly, comforting herself. "Aris is very good, even too good to be rude." (HD, 2008:09)	Consider the norm conditions by thinking good about friends.
	"So, how should I be now? How?! Anna's screaming in her heart. "Will I meet his demands? Oh, no! I will not betray my family! I will not betray the father of my children, no matter how much I do not love him!" (HD, 2008:27-28)	Keep considering loyalty , even if it does not match Anna's Id.
	"I already have a man. He has become the father of my two children. Really, I really don't love him. And I never understood why I got entangled in being his wife. However, this marriage is legal. Laws, churches, and customs have confirmed it! I have to be loyal. I must accept this situation with an open heart!" (HD, 2008.31-32)	I have to be faithful , for the sake of the law of norms in society.
	"So, once in two days Anna always took the time to visit Aris' mother. Bringing a cake made by herself, bread, milk or anything that she thought could please the old woman. Anna thought that by doing good to Aunt Lin-\ Aris's mom, at least some of sin against Aris had been forgiven. (HD, 2008:129)	Good deeds are the norm law in society for a better relationship.
	"It's very difficult for Anna not to forgive Frans for his lewdness. She thought she also needed forgiveness from Frans. No matter how painful her heart is, it's still better. Because that woman was not a good woman, not a young wife or anything like that. Then Anna sighed, "Frans, do you want to forgive me?". Her voice was very weak; a touch penetrated to Frans' soul. And the man was stunned. Almost couldn't believe it. Because he was already sure that Anna would swear at him completely. At first he had given up. However, what came out of Anna's mouth was not a curse. But a very weak sigh of pity. "Frans," Anna repeated again, weaker. "You want to take us back?" (HD, 2008:217)	For the sake of the norm in society Anna was willing to apologize.

Table 6
Superego Data and its interpretation of "Sebuah Usaha Melupakan" Novel

Personality Structure	Data	Interpretation
	"I always really hope. May the universe always bring us closer," (P. 28)	Hope involving the universe
	"... I can slowly achieve my dreams one by one..." (p. 49)	Achieving something normally
	'Don't give up on staying with me. Don't let weakness make us bad. Because, someday I want to go home with a happy heart. I want to see you waiting for longing." (p. 72).	Don't give up on difficult condition
	"If I could, I would love to erase you from a torturous memory. There is not a single thing I will let to stab myself and make the memory feel painful..." (p. 149)	Power outside of self

"... I had run away from my town. Spending sad days in another city to kill painful time. I can't even believe it..." (p. 153)	Avoid conflict
"... I want to laugh as loudly as I can, look into your eyes and believe you're joking..." (p. 225)	Can't believe reality
"You are the home to return to, the part of life that is the reason for fighting. Encouragement in times of fatigue. Someone who keeps me feeling recovered after being hurt." (p. 289).	The spirit of fighting because there are conditions that force to fight
"I just want us to look each other in the eye. Then, feel what you feel in your chest. The vibration that grow are feelings that fall... it is something people call love". (Page 298).	Reveal feelings in reality
"Now believe me. Your mother is the only woman who won't give up. No matter what I do, she'll stay with me. That's what makes you present as a part of my life. Read the books I write, learn that you can enjoy your heartbreak without crying." (P. 300).	All forms of mental state can be experienced by a person.

Table 7
Id's Interpretation Result of Main Character of The Novels

Personality Structure	Novel Interpretation Results	
	Harga Diri	Sebuah Usaha Melupakan
Id	Anna's inner instincts are followed without being controlled by the super ego aspect. Because Anna 'agreed' to Aris' wishes. The id is a need from within humans according to Sigmud Freud's theory.	The hallucination of "I" character is a manifestation of the fulfilment of Id's needs.
	Anna was shaken and scared. Aris came to see her. This fear arises naturally. This becomes id's need that should soon be avoided .	The desire to be with 'you' until then is the longing of "I", which is the form of the Id.
	Anna's maternal instincts emerged as manifestations of her actions. Between love for her child or admitting mistakes	Togetherness becomes longing of "I" . This is the Id of "me" / "I"
	Instinct melts arrogance and supports her husband, Frans', career. This instinct arises from within Anna at her own consideration without taking into account of external conditions or balance with the environment.	The ambition of 'he' who wants 'you', be the embodiment of the Id of 'me'.
	Anna's desire to prevent Aris from marrying another woman. Whatever is done to achieve that goal. This is a condition of the satisfying of Anna's desire .	Unexpected loss , although it must be experienced. It's a sign that there's a need that can't be met.
		Ready to be a place to lean. It was a call from within the body of the Id of 'me'

Tabel 8
Ego's Interpretation Result of Main Character of The Novels

Personality Structure	Novel Interpretation Results	
	Harga Diri	Sebuah Usaha Melupakan
Ego	The determination to keep fighting is a sign of meeting the needs of Anna.	Expectation that should occur because it is not merely a necessity, but is real and does not violate the norm. This is the ego of 'me'.
	Firm on the principle of getting divorced without involving conditions outside Anna.	Hopes to enjoy the pleasant conditions that are almost real.
	The nature of surrender and hope for a better life.	Be patient, from 'me' is the embodiment of the 'ego' aspect.

	Unsatisfied conditions. To always keep fighting. It is the 'ego' of 'me'.
	Hope to please friends. It is the element of the 'ego' which has taken into account of Id's needs, and superego's consideration.
	Remain friends in joy and sorrow.
	Calm is needed to overcome the problem even though it is not easy. This is embodiment of the 'ego' aspect in 'me'.
	Make dream happens with patience.
	Forgetting the past.
	Forgetting the past.
	Learn to let go.
	The spirit of rising from the past.
	Commitment to self to work hard
	The spirit to live together
	To make friends happy.
	Choose carefully
	To make friends happy.
	Living together sincerely

Tabel 9
Super Ego's Interpretation Result of Main Character of The Novels

Personality Structure	Novel Interpretation Results	
	Harga Diri	Sebuah Usaha Melupakan
Superego	Consider the norm conditions by thinking good about friends.	Hope involving the universe
	Keep considering loyalty , even if it does not match Anna's Id.	Achieving something normally
	I have to be faithful , for the sake of the law of norms in society.	Don't give up on difficult condition
	Good deeds are the norm law in society for a better relationship.	Power outside of self
	For the sake of the norm in society Anna was willing to apologize.	Avoid conflict
		Can't believe reality
		The spirit of fighting because there are conditions that force to fight
		Reveal feelings in reality
	All forms of mental state can be experienced by a person.	

E. Conclusion

Based on the data analysis that has been done, it can be concluded that the characters described by the author in the novel are based on Sigmund Freud's Personality theory, namely the Id of the character who fulfils desires, ambitions, and hallucinations. The ego aspect is determined, hopes for a better life, does not violate norms, makes friends happy, lives together sincerely. The superego aspect thinks good towards others, considers loyalty, does good to others, is willing to apologize.

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